

SOURCE INFLUENCES ON THE EXCITATION OF GUIDED ELASTIC WAVES IN ANISOTROPIC LAYERS

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ABSTRACT

The use of guided elastic waves for the nondestructive evaluation of composite materials is becoming increasingly popular due to the unique properties of such waves. Larger areas can be examined for single pulse excitation compared to point by point bulk wave inspection techniques. In contrast to bulk wave propagation, there are an infinite number of guided wave modes from which to choose. Because each mode is in many ways different than the others, the individual modes will be more or less sensitive to the quantity being measured and hence, selection of an appropriate mode becomes critical to the success of an inspection technique. This paper deals with the next step in the inspection process, namely, the generation of the mode which has been selected for use. An acousto-ultrasonics experimental procedure is employed utilizing normal incidence, rectangular piezoelectric transducers. Drawing on the results of previous theoretical studies, practical conclusions are drawn about the parameters of the inspection probe such as its frequency content, size, pressure distribution and incident angle to isolate as much as possible a particular mode from among the many possible modes of the structure.

1. Introduction

Guided waves are finding an increased usage among the nondestructive evaluation (NDE) community for both defect detection and material characterization purposes. The unique properties of the individual guided wave modes offer a host of possibilities for non-destructively probing the material of which the layer is composed. Because of the different displacement (and all other) field distributions of the different modes, they each interact differently with the material composing the layer, and hence each carries useful information about the constitution and/or state of the layer. Before one can fully utilize the diverse nature of the different modes however, it is necessary to understand fully the manner in which the individual guided wave modes can be introduced into the layer by applied surface loading.

In a recent paper^[1], the excitation of an arbitrarily anisotropic (i.e. 21 independent elastic moduli) layer due to arbitrarily applied, time harmonic surface tractions was solved utilizing the normal mode expansion technique^[2-3]. The displacement and traction fields in the loaded layer were expanded in terms of the "normal modes" of the layer (i.e. the mode fields in the free layer) multiplied by unknown amplitudes. In this paper, the results of the previous general theoretical study are examined for specific types of composite layers, and experiments are performed to compare with the theoretical model.

2. Normal Modes

For wave motion in anisotropic layers, it is found that an assumed solution for the particle displacement field of the form,

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \mathbf{u}(x_1)e^{i2\pi f(x_2/c-t)} \quad (1)$$

will only satisfy the governing elasticity equations^[4] and boundary conditions if a certain relation holds between the frequency f (times layer thickness, d) and the phase velocity, c . This is the so-called dispersion relation for the layer which can be written symbolically in the form,

$$\Omega(c, fd, C_{ij}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

In Eq. (2), C_{ij} represents the elastic constants of the layer. The equation symbolized in Eq. (2) is usually transcendental and therefore, for any given frequency f , it admits an infinite number of solutions (counting real, imaginary and complex roots) for the phase velocity c .

Figure 1 is a typical plot of the real roots of the dispersion equation for an orthotropic graphite epoxy composite for propagation along a symmetry plane. Each continuous curve is termed a *mode* of the structure, and each point on each curve (i.e. for any frequency thickness product) represents an undamped propagating wave with its own unique displacement and stress field distributions, phase and group velocities, etc. It can be seen that as fd increases, so does the number of propagating modes. The frequency value below which a given mode ceases to propagate (i.e. its phase velocity becomes imaginary or complex) is termed the cut-off frequency of that mode. The phase velocity and frequency thickness ranges were chosen to allow later comparison with experiments.

3. Loaded Layer

The dispersion curves of Fig. 1. represent waves which can exist in the layer with *no externally applied loads*. If a distribution of forces of a given frequency f_o , is applied to the boundaries of the layer, then, in general, all of the modes available at that particular $f_o d$ value will be generated with varying amplitudes. For a given excitation frequency, some of the modes may be below cut-off and hence propagate, whereas others may be above cut-off and therefore represent non-propagating disturbances localized near the source which excites them.

FIG 1. Dispersion curves for typical orthotropic composite. (Propagation in a symmetry plane)

The relative amplitudes with which each of the propagating modes is excited depends essentially on the *distribution* of the applied forces, as well as the field distributions of the mode at the fd value chosen. A particularly common way of generating guided waves is with the wedge technique depicted in Fig. 2. In this technique, a piezoelectric transducer is placed on a wedge which is inclined at some angle θ_i to the normal of the layer, and coupled to the layer by a thin layer of oil or water. The parameters of primary importance in this type of loading are the size of the transducer, D , its central frequency f_o and frequency bandwidth, σ_f , the pressure distribution across its face, $p(\alpha)$, and the incident angle θ_i .

FIG 2. Wedge method of exciting guided waves

If the transducer vibrates at the single frequency f_o , and the wedge is coupled to the layer via a non-viscous liquid so that only normal tractions are transferred, it has been shown⁽¹⁾ that the amplitude with which each propagating mode is excited, A_μ , can be written as the product of four terms,

$$A_{\pm\mu}(z) = \mathcal{G}\mathcal{F}^{(\pm)} E_{\pm\mu} e^{\mp i\beta_\mu z} \quad (3)$$

The function \mathcal{G} represents a numerical factor which depends solely on the output power of the transducer. For non-harmonic loading, the function \mathcal{G} is replaced by the Fourier transform of the time variation of the source, and an integration over frequency must then be performed. The function $E_{\pm\mu}$, termed the "excitability" function of mode μ depends only on properties of the mode which is being excited and *not* on the properties of the source used for excitation. The function $\mathcal{F}^{(\pm)}$ depends only on properties of the transducer and wedge used to excite the layer. The product function, $\mathcal{F}\mathcal{G}$ which is also dependent only on transducer parameters, is termed the "excitation" function of the source. The amplitude with which guided waves are generated is therefore seen to be proportional to the product of the excitation function, $\mathcal{F}\mathcal{G}$, determined by transducer and wedge parameters, and the excitability function, $E_{\pm\mu}$, which depends on which mode is excited and where on its dispersion curve it is excited. This paper is concerned with the excitation function and how it is affected by various transducer - wedge parameters.

4. Piston source

In the case that the pressure distribution is uniform across the face of the transducer, the function $p(\alpha)$ becomes some constant, say $\sigma_o(f)$, (dependent only on frequency, f) for $|\alpha| < D/2$ and zero for $|\alpha| > D/2$. In this case, Eq. (9) for the excitation amplitudes becomes,

$$A_{\pm\mu}(z) = \frac{\overbrace{\sigma_o(f)|R(\theta_i)|}^{\mathcal{G}}}{4} \frac{\overbrace{\tilde{v}_{\pm\mu y}(b/2)}^{E_{\pm\mu}}}{P_{\mu\mu}} \overbrace{2 \frac{\sin\left(\frac{(\beta_\mu \mp k_w \sin \theta_i)D}{2 \cos \theta_i}\right)}{(\beta_\mu \mp k_w \sin \theta_i)}}^{\mathcal{F}^{(\pm)}}} e^{\mp i\beta_\mu z} \quad (4)$$

where the positive amplitudes are valid for $z \geq L$ and the negative amplitudes for $z \leq -L$.

As can be seen, the excitation amplitudes are a function of the several parameters including the diameter of the source (D), its longitudinal wave speed ($k_w = 2\pi f/V_{\text{shoe}}$), and the incident angle, θ_i , all contained in the \mathcal{F} function. β_μ denotes the (real) wavenumber of generated mode μ , $P_{\mu\mu}$ denotes the time averaged power carried by the mode per unit waveguide width, and $\tilde{v}_{\pm\mu y}(b/2)$ denotes the "y" component of particle velocity at the upper surface of the layer.

Of interest in this paper is the function, \mathcal{F} , of the source for the particular case of normal incidence loading ($\theta_i = 0$). In this case, the \mathcal{F} reduces to,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{F}^{(\pm)} &= \frac{\sin(\beta_\mu D/2)}{\beta_\mu} \\ &= V_{\text{ph}}^\mu \frac{\sin(\omega D/2V_{\text{ph}}^\mu)}{\omega} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where V_{ph}^μ denotes the phase velocity of mode μ , given by $V_{\text{ph}}^\mu = \omega/\beta_\mu$.

Equation 5 has very important practical ramifications. Perhaps the most important conclusion which can be drawn from Eq. (5), is the fact that, when using finite sources,

a spectrum of phase velocities is generated, *not a single phase velocity* as given by the conventional Snell's law for infinite plane wave excitation. Examining the function \mathcal{F} in more detail, it can be seen that, for normal incidence loading, it will be a maximum when $\beta_\mu \rightarrow 0$, or equivalently, $V_{ph}^\mu \rightarrow \infty$. This means that *a normal incidence source is most efficient at exciting waveguide modes at large values of phase velocity*. The efficiency with which a normal incidence source can excite waveguide modes at lower phase velocities depends upon the frequency of the source and its width, D .

Figure 3 shows a plot of \mathcal{F} as given by Eq. (5) for two different size transducers, $D = 3.175$ mm, and $D = 12.7$ mm, each normalized independently by the respective value of \mathcal{F} at $\beta = 0$. The abscissa is labelled by both wavenumber, β , and phase velocity V_{ph} , with an assumed frequency of 1.0 MHz. A decibel scale was used for the ordinate. As can be seen from Fig. 3, \mathcal{F} for the larger diameter source decreases more rapidly from its maximum at $\beta = 0$, ($V_{ph} \rightarrow \infty$) than the smaller diameter source. In fact, Fig. 3 shows that the 12.7 mm source would generate modes with a phase velocity of 20.0 mm/ μ sec with 6 dB less amplitude than those with infinite (or very large) phase velocity, whereas the 3.175 mm source would excite modes with $V_{ph} = 3.0$ at 6 dB down as compared to the excitation at $V_{ph} \rightarrow \infty$.

Fig. 3. \mathcal{F} versus β and V_{ph} for two different size transducers. Solid: $D = 12.7$ mm; Dashed: $D = 3.175$ mm.

One conclusion to be drawn from Fig. 3 is that if the goal is to generate modes with small phase velocities (using normal incidence loading), then the source diameter should be kept as small as possible in order to broaden the phase velocity spectrum of the source to include smaller phase velocities. Of course, the smaller source will mean a loss of output energy which must be compensated for by increasing the output power of the source.

5. Sample Experiments

As an example of how the dispersion curves of a structure can be used to predict the wave motion generated in it by applied surface loads, experiments were performed on a $[0/\pm 20/0]$ composite panel made of graphite epoxy prepreg tape. The dimensions of the

Fig. 4. Experimental Set-up

panel were approximately 3.13 mm by 305 mm by 305 mm. Experiments were performed using two sets of normal incidence transducers of different widths (D), both driven at 1.0 MHz with a tone burst function generator. The experimental setup is shown in Fig. 4. One transducer acts as a sender of ultrasonic waves, and the other matched transducer as a receiver. The width of the two sets of transducers, D , were 12.7 and 3.175 mm, which were the values used when plotting the function \mathcal{F} in Fig. 3.

As can be seen from Fig. 3, theory predicts that the 12.7 mm width source would excite most efficiently (say with -6 dB amplitude as compared to the maximum) at 1 MHz, modes with phase velocities above 20 mm/ μ sec, whereas the 3.175 mm width source would efficiently excite modes with phase velocities ranging down to approximately 3.0 mm/ μ sec. That this is the case is partially verified by examining Figs. 5a and b along with the dispersion curves presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 5a is the frequency (times plate thickness) spectrum of the received RF signal when using the 12.7 mm source. Several distinct, almost equally spaced peaks appear, which correspond to some of the modes which appear in Fig. 3 for large phase velocity. Looking at the dispersion curves of Fig. 3, for large values of phase velocity, it will be observed that the curves are almost vertical in this region. There are, however, approximately 7 modes in the fd range 0.0 - 6.0 plotted in Figs. 5. This means that, of the seven modes, some were generated by the source while others were not efficiently generated. This has to do with the excitability functions, $E_{\pm\mu}$, of the individual modes (see Eqs. 3-4) as will be discussed shortly.

Figure 5b shows the results obtained when using the smaller width (3.175 mm) source. Several features should be noted. First of all, each of the peaks have been shifted to the right (larger fd values) in accord with the fact that each of the dispersion curves of the structure increases in fd as the phase velocity decreases. Another feature to note is the fact that there are more peaks obtained when using the smaller source that when using the larger one. This is partially due to the fact that at lower phase velocities (which the small source excites more efficiently than the large source) many of the modes are more excitable than they are at high phase velocities due to their vibrational characteristics.

The fact that not all of the modes of the structure are excited by the normal incidence loading (especially with the large width source) is due to the different vibrational

Fig. 5a. Frequency (times thickness) spectrum of received signal using 12.7 mm source

Fig. 5b. Frequency (times thickness) spectrum of received signal using 3.175 mm source

characteristics of the individual modes. As shown by Eq. (6), the amplitude with which each mode is generated is proportional to the “ y ” component of the particle velocity (or displacement) field at the upper surface of the layer. The larger this component of displacement, the more efficiently the mode can be generated. Fig. 6a and b are plots of the normalized particle displacement fields for the first two modes ($fd_1 = 0.97$ MHz·mm, $fd_2 = 1.27$ MHz·mm) at $V_{ph} = 30$ mm/ μ sec. As can be seen, the mode at $fd = 0.97$ MHz·mm has a dominant in plane (u_x) displacement at the upper surface ($\bar{y} = +1$) and almost no out of plane (u_y) displacement there, whereas the mode at $fd = 1.27$ MHz·mm has just the opposite behaviour. This explains why the lower fd mode was not excited (see Figs. 1, 5a) by the large source whereas the second mode was.

6. Conclusions

The use of finite sized transducers to excite waves in layers has been discussed and it has been shown that as a result of the finite size, a spectrum of phase velocities is generated as opposed to the single phase velocity obtained from the phase matching principle (Snell’s law) for infinite plane wave excitation. For normal incidence, modes with infinite phase velocity are generated most efficiently, and the modes (or regions of dispersion curves) with

Fig. 6a. Normalized displacement fields for mode at $V_{ph} = 30.0 \text{ mm}/\mu\text{sec}$, $fd = 0.97 \text{ MHz-mm}$ showing dominance of in-plane displacement u_x at surfaces. Solid line u_x ; Dashed line u_y .

Fig. 6b. Normalized displacement fields for mode at $V_{ph} = 30.0 \text{ mm}/\mu\text{sec}$, $fd = 1.27 \text{ MHz-mm}$ showing dominance of out-of-plane displacement u_y at surfaces. Solid line u_x ; Dashed line u_y

lower phase velocities are generated more efficiently with smaller sources than with larger ones. Experiments utilizing an acousto-ultrasonics test mode have been reported which qualitatively support the conclusions predicted from theory.

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